

Anomaly Detection on Sparse Data with Autoencoders

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Abstract

An autoencoder model is applied to predict anomalies in tax form data consisting of hundreds of sparse, irregularly distributed features. Techniques borrowed from literature and customized for this use case are applied to address the sparsity of the data and protect against potentially contaminated (i.e., non-compliant) data affecting model training. These techniques are studied and compared to existing classified forms with known anomalies. Existing approaches required a priori domain knowledge, manual decision-making, and forced Gaussian transformations on the data. Initial stages of testing show promising results against these methods once further refined and do so without any of the existing method constraints.

Key Words: Sparse data, unsupervised, deep learning, autoencoder, deep anomaly detection

1. Introduction

The Internal Revenue Service (IRS) dedicates extensive resources to manual detection of data errors in form submissions. The manual review process, where employees identify anomalous form values by hand, is both time-consuming and labor intensive. Replicating the manual review process with a model-based approach frees up scarce resources, ensures consistency, and reduces certain potential biases. The goal is to detect anomalous data across over 100 million tax returns with accuracy by designing a model-based approach.

Challenges exist due to both the nature of the data and the limitations of computational resources available. Evaluating over 100 million tax returns means that manual methods are impractical at scale. Because taxpayers populate only lines that apply to them, most forms can be represented as a sparse matrix. The natural sparsity of features can complicate analysis and must be handled appropriately with a specialized sparse data approach. A computationally efficient design and a complex model is required.

Unsupervised approaches are preferred for several reasons. First, a limited set of labeled data is available. Additional labels come at a prohibitive cost for the IRS to create. Furthermore, data and signatures of anomalies change over population and time as taxpayer data varies from year to year. Much of the data is Pareto and irregularly distributed, so model non-normality and non-linear relationships must be handled through transformations or through model attributes. Unsupervised anomaly detection approaches on sparse form data have previously been studied by Parker *et al.*^{3,4}. We propose an autoencoder model as an alternative approach to this anomaly detection problem.

2. Previous Research in the Problem Space

Covariance methods have been studied to identify tax errors^{3,4}. These approaches have been found to rival manual review processes in output quality.

To detect anomalies at the form level, the one-sided multivariate test, as described in Kudo 1963¹ and Yamamoto 1997⁵, was found to be highly effective. This test allows for the inclusion of

directionality into decision rules that can be set to focus on expected direction of anomalies if the taxpayer is attempting to reduce their overall tax liability. The multivariate one-sided test is designed to prioritize anomalies of a pre-determined type.

Parker *et al.*^{3,4} assumed that the data follows a multivariate Gaussian distribution with a sparse mean vector μ ; $\mu' = (\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_k)$ and sparse covariance estimation R . The following test was set:

$$y \sim N(\mu + \theta\delta, R)$$

Normal Forms; $\theta_i = 0 \ (i = 1, 2, \dots, k)$
Anomalous Forms; $\theta_i \delta \geq 0 \ (i = 1, 2, \dots, k)$

Where

$$\delta \in \{-1, 1, 0\} \text{ indicating the direction of anomaly of interest}$$

This resulted in the following likelihood ratio test:

$$\frac{\max_{\theta} p(y + \theta; \mu, R)}{p(y; \mu, R)}$$

Fixed transforms to the data were enforced to make the data Gaussian as most of the features were irregularly distributed. While this method was shown to be comparable to manual processes, there is potentially more room for improvement by capturing non-linear relationships between features and irregular distributions. Another disadvantage is that the line item direction of interest must be established before training to take advantage of one-sided functionality. This requires both manual decision-making on line item directionalities as well as domain knowledge. Testing these rules of line item direction is time-consuming, and it can be difficult to detect incorrect directionalities.

3. Autoencoder Approach

3.1 Background

An autoencoder is a deep learning technique that uses neural networks to learn compressed data encodings by capturing the underlying relationships in a population of data. It forces the reduction of input data down to a much smaller size representation of the data, and then attempts to reconstruct the data input with minimal loss.

For an autoencoder to learn the reconstruction of inputs, the training data is passed through the network many times; each time, the model assesses its ability to reconstruct cases (loss function) and makes corresponding adjustments to improve reconstruction.

This model differs from our previous research in that it has the potential to consider unspecified and non-linear relationships. It requires no a priori knowledge on which line items are critical or the direction of specific lines. Additionally, the initial layers of an autoencoder model effectively

execute much of the basic data preprocessing, saving additional time and experimentation in research.

When designed for anomaly detection in the tax space, autoencoders can learn from a theoretically “normal” set of data (i.e., compliant tax forms) to identify deviations from “normal” behavior (i.e., non-compliance). The autoencoder learns low-dimensional, condensed representations of forms based on the patterns and relationships in the input data. The autoencoder then reconstructs those forms from the condensed representation by first providing predicted values for each line-item. The differences between line item predictions and actual line item values are evaluated across all line items to derive a case-level score representing the overall anomalousness of a form. We know our training data consists of mostly “normal” forms but also is contaminated with some unknown amount of “not normal” forms. To address this contamination, as well as the underlying sparsity of the data, we made several modifications to the training and scoring process.

3.2 Training and Scoring Modifications

To account for the sparsity of the data, sparse mean squared error (MSE) was used as a customized approach for both the loss calculation in training and the objective function in scoring. Errors corresponding to missing values were excluded from the MSE calculation to avoid skewing the relationships learned during training. This allowed for direct calculation of loss without imputation of missing values.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{k_{filled}} \sum_{j=1}^{k_{filled}} (\text{populated line}_j - \text{predicted line}_j)^2$$

In an ideal scenario, autoencoders are built only on “normal” data or with just a small volume of anomalous data, so that reconstruction is optimized on normal cases. The training data here is mostly unlabeled and is likely contaminated with “not normal” cases at an unknown rate. Because of this contamination, an autoencoder model may learn representations of both not normal and normal data equally well over time and not be able to distinguish between the two classes of data.

Percentile loss (PL) training² was introduced to avoid learning patterns from the most anomalous cases. We define an upper-bound threshold (e.g., $q = 75\%$) and a reconstruction error in each mini-batch corresponding to that percentile P_q . With this threshold in place, we update parameters based only on data points with reconstruction errors *below* P_q . This adaptation of the loss function reduces the probability of anomalous cases disproportionately contributing to parameter updates during the training process. This process can be expressed as follows:

$$L = \frac{1}{|B|} \sum_{i \in B} MSE_i$$

Where

$$B = \{i \in \text{Current Batch} \mid MSE_i \leq P_q\}$$

Additionally, a modified version of traditional PL training as defined by Merrill and Eskandarian² was tested by discarding losses from only a random subset of the largest losses. The equation below describes how this modification is performed. For example, if $q = 0.70$, losses below the 70th percentile would still be included in the loss calculation, but so would half of losses between the 70th and 85th percentile (all losses between the 85th and 100th percentile would still be excluded). This probabilistic approach allows for less severe cuts to the set of data points included in the loss calculation meaning some, but not all, of the largest losses in each batch still affect the model.

$$L = \frac{1}{|B|} \sum_{i \in B} MSE_i$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned}
B &= B_{orig} \cup B_{new} \\
B_{orig} &= \{i \in \text{Current Batch} \mid MSE_i \leq P_q\} \\
B_{new} &= \{i \in \text{Current Batch} \mid P_q < MSE_i \leq P_{(1+q)/2}; \text{Prob}(i \in B_{new}) = 0.5\}
\end{aligned}$$

To further reduce contamination from anomalous cases during the training process, cumulative error scoring² was implemented, which sums the history of reconstruction errors over each epoch throughout training to identify anomalies, with the assumption that the model takes longer to learn anomalous patterns. One disadvantage of this scoring method is that unlike scoring based on reconstruction errors, cumulative error scoring cannot be easily applied to new data (i.e., data that has not been part of the training process).

A modified version of the cumulative error scoring approach was also tested, where reconstruction errors were summed only after the first five epochs. This was meant to address the tendency for cumulative error scores to be skewed by larger errors in the earliest epochs (i.e., if performance was poor in the first epoch, then performance based on cumulative errors tended to be worse, even after many epochs).

Lastly, it was found that the final AUC varied when running multiple trials with the same parameters, so an ensemble of scores from each trial was used to generate ROC curves for each experiment, thereby increasing the stability of the ROC curves with this novel approach. Because scores in one trial could be higher on average than scores in another trial, the ensemble was implemented by scaling the scores within each trial to between 0 and 1, then summing the scaled scores across trials for each return. Generally, five trials were used for each experiment. While more trials would further increase the stability of model performance, five trials were found to be sufficient for early research.

4. Implementation and Numerical Results

4.1 Implementation

The techniques of section 3.2 were executed in Python using the PyTorch library as the primary tool for model building. A NVIDIA DGX GPU server was leveraged to improve computational efficiency of modeling such a large, high dimensional dataset.

For the model architecture, SeLu was used for each hidden layer activation function and Tanh for the output activation function. There were five hidden linear layers with [100, 80, 64, 32, 8] neurons per layer for the encoder step and the reverse for the decoder step. Maximum Absolute Value was used as the data scaling function.

4.2 Results

The approaches described here were tested using a sample of an anonymized form database consisting of $n = \sim 430,000$ entities from tax filings from 2014-2016 who had each populated some or all of $k = \sim 240$ real-valued form fields on an individual 1040 US tax return and aggregated schedules. This data is populated on a yearly basis by taxpayers to calculate their tax liability and contains information about a wide variety of earnings, assets, expenses, and business ownership. To measure anomaly detection performance, we used 10,000 manually evaluated forms from the same time period.

Initial models were generated using line items from the primary filing form (i.e., 20-40 features) to streamline training. However, these models produced weak results, so subsequent models included line items from all relevant forms (i.e., 100+ features). Any line items containing categorical data were excluded from the model.

Table 1 shows the parameter space tested to date, with bold values indicating the best performing combination of parameters. The autoencoder anomaly detection framework includes many different parameters that can be tuned to maximize performance, including the scoring modifications discussed previously (e.g., PL threshold). With such a large parameter space and long runtimes required to train each new model on the dataset, it was not practical to perform an exhaustive grid

search of all possible parameter combinations. Most testing focused on finding the optimal value for the PL threshold and the optimal number of epochs at which to stop training; several different values were also tested for batch size, learning rate, and weight decay, but these values were held constant for most experiments.

Table 1: Parameter Space Tested

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value(s)</i>
Batch size	[400, 1000, 2000, 10000 , 50000]
Epochs	[1, 5, 20, 40, 60 , 100, 200]
Learning rate	[8e-4, 8e-5 , 8e-6]
Weight decay	[1e-8 , 2e-8, 4e-8]
PL threshold	[0.5, 0.6, 0.65, 0.7, 0.75 , 0.8, 0.85, 0.9, 0.95]
Number of trials	5

Experiments were mainly evaluated based on area under the ROC curve (AUC) within the labeled data, using the reconstruction error and cumulative error as anomaly scores. Figure 1 shows a representative example of ensembling results across five trials with the same set of parameters. Note that this experiment used the modified cumulative error discussed in section 3.2, so the cumulative error AUC (orange line) starts at 5 epochs (at which point the reconstruction and cumulative error AUCs are equal). Plots of AUC vs epoch were used to understand how performance changed throughout the training process and what number of epochs would represent an appropriate stopping point.

Figure 1: AUC vs Epoch - Ensemble of Anomaly Scores Across Trials

Figure 2 shows the ROC curve for the best performing autoencoder model to date. These results were also obtained by ensembling anomaly scores across five trials. The autoencoder’s AUC is close to 0.60 ± 0.02 using non-accumulated reconstruction error, with AUC up to 0.65 observed during some trials. For comparison, existing models (i.e., covariance; not shown) achieve up to 0.7 AUC.

Figure 2: Champion Autoencoder Model

5. Discussion

Reconstruction error tended to outperform cumulative error as a method for anomaly scoring. When aggregating results across multiple trials, peak reconstruction error AUC was reliably near 20 epochs, and AUC tended to only vary by about .01 through 40+ remaining epochs. The modifications to PL training and cumulative error scoring discussed in section 3.2 did not significantly impact performance, with a slight boost in AUC observed for the modified cumulative error scoring.

Initial results with relatively limited testing suggest that an autoencoder approach to anomaly detection could rival existing processes, especially with further testing. Our research, while slightly lower in performance, required no a priori domain knowledge of the line items' criticality or direction, which was a key component to previous approaches. Introducing similar rules could help improve future autoencoder performance.

Additional areas for continued research include:

- Early stopping mechanisms – i.e., automate process for determining the optimal point at which to stop training, rather than using a fixed number of epochs
- More tuning of existing parameters, including modifications to PL training and cumulative error scoring (e.g., smoother probabilistic PL threshold, varied “start” epoch for cumulative error scoring)
- More complex model structures (e.g., convolutional and/or dropout layers) – this could allow for more complex representations of anomalousness
- Semi-supervised approaches using limited labeled data
- Additional features (i.e., not directly from forms)

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